
**A Study On Marketing Prospective For The Outcome Of Investment In
Online Business**

Dr. Vrishali Kakasaheb Madne

*Assistant Professor Department of Commerce,
Abasaheb Parvekar Mahavidyalay, Yavatmal.*

Corresponding Author – Dr. Vrishali Kakasaheb Madne

DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.15560661

Abstract:

Prediction about the future of marketing is not possible for human, Our prediction is about the game changer or future market player who can control the market world. The vision of my study is to find the future marketing investment and its effect in consumer mind in online business. How it reflects to the success of brand and products. Now days we have a many of advertisement methods because of unlimited and different types of customer in the world. We cannot expect that all people taste and preference will be same and real fact it must differ, our business marketing plan is one of the most crucial elements of our overall proposal. As a social animal we never run on same track we always need a track which is faster and shortest way to reach our targets. As human we first use our legs to travel then animal next machines and at last planning for time travel same things happen in the market from barter system to now online marketing.

Keywords: Marketing, Consumer, Online Business

Introduction:

A new organization will find it extremely difficult to be successful one in a crowded marketplace because with a public distracted by many stimuli. A marketing object for organizations with public awareness. That will be a successful marketing campaign in the future, It made a splash by running provocative ads in high-profile places, such as during the Super Bowl. The whole world is moving fast so whatever is to be done is to be done now itself. That's what people are doing. Just imagine how many internet marketing alerts you receive on hourly basis. And how many of them are promotional base. These

promotions bring you an infinite variety of choice of consumer goods and services. Therefore, the whole world has gone. Know the potential of your marketing device. Customer is the king' has been a dominating marketing mantra since true quite still now. In other words, when company become loyal to the brand that wins them. Therefore, is the place where it all begins. It's based on the market research that products and services are designed. The final phase of the marketing is to advertise them to the target customer. All activities on the part of a business end here to move along with risk to earn more. If they pass a product or service it the foundation of the relationship

between a brand and its customers is laid. Brand must build on it by upgrading their product or service. If they won't do this, their competitors surely caper the inroads into their hard win market.

Statement of the Problem:

Identifying problem and opportunities in the future markets that helps in identifying new market opportunities for new brand and new products. It provides information on market share, nature of competition, customer satisfaction levels, sales performances, channel of distribution along with market position of the firm. This helps the firms in solving the both internal and external problems. Companies or organizations use marketing research to manage the risks of investments which is associated with offering new products and services. These organizations don't want to spend too much money developing a product line so that research indicates will be unsuccessful. Some problems make marketing research costly which make cost price higher and produce results of questionable value for the organization.

The Significance of the Market Study:

Most investors want to make investments in a safe environment so that they get sky-high returns as fast as possible and also without the risk of losing the principal amount. And this is the main reason why many investors are always on the lookout for top investment plans so that they can earn double their money in few days, months or years. The risk of losing a principal of capital is high unless option for stop loss money to curtail losses. In stop-loss

mean which is the one of place an advance order to sell a stock at a specific price and time. To reduce the risk to certain extent and they could diversify across sectors and market capitalizations. A new product to market is produced by large companies will do the significant test marketing and product either selecting consumers to try the product or showing and explaining the product's benefits to consumer review their opinions about it. Market research means keeping closely watching on our major competitor growth particularly what type of strategies they have deployed to capture additional number of customers that are potentially our customers it even affect our customer relationship also so plan to maintain smooth relationship with odd one.

Objectives:

1. To implement a new online shopping business.
2. To find the lever of investor for the new business.
3. To help the local retailer to survey in the market.
4. To know why Amazon is best in online shopping.
5. To find shopping experience in Amazon.

Limitation

1. Business cannot be done with all retailers.
2. Only metro and main cities can be covered easily.
3. It can not stop showroom experiences.

Research Methodology:

Experimental research is a study that strictly adheres to a scientific research design which is used as research methodology. It includes a hypothesis, a variable that can be manipulated by the researcher, and variables that can be measured, calculated and compared. Most importantly, experimental research is completed in a controlled environment. The researcher collects data and results will either support or reject the hypothesis. This method of research is referred to a hypothesis testing or a deductive research method. Experimental research seeks to determine a relationship between two variables the dependent variable and the independent variable. After completing an experimental research study all about a correlation between a specific aspect of an entity and the variable being studied is either supported or rejected. Data in experimental research must be able to be quantified, or measured, These types of observations help supplement the measurements taken throughout the experiment.

Primary Data & Secondary Data:

Primary Data: Primary data have been collected from the newly implemented business processes in the online business world.

Secondary Data: Secondary data have been collected from different sources such as journals, books, internet and other sources.

Future New Company:

Just imagine a new company came with a new delivery plan like when a customer will place the order like previous one we can take same fast track watch now as soon as

company received order it will forward to the local fast track watch at the same time the delivery boy also received it and will pack the item and give to delivery boy at last consumer will get it. Below I am comparing my business process with Amazon.

New Company Delivery Process:

1. Customer will place the order by using app or website.
2. Company will receive the order & Company will forward order to local brand showroom partner.
3. Showroom partner will aspect order & Customer will as so know on which branch that product will arrive.
4. Delivery boy will get order where to receive order and detail of the order also Showroom branch will get detail about delivery boy.
5. Delivery boy will check pack and get address of customer & Customer will get order.

Amazon Delivery Process:

1. Customer will place the order by using website or app. Example watch.
2. Amazon will confirm order as per the customer instruction.
3. Amazon will purchase order for its supplier. Example if they received order of fast track watch, Amazon will purchase watch from fast track Company itself.
4. Particular watch will be packed with customer order id and other required details.
5. Items will be shipped as per the location.

6. Item will be reached local distribution office and delivery boy will get package as per the divided location.
7. Delivery boy will deliver the item to customer as per the printed locational id.

Conclusion:

In Online platform as per the Indian government to the policy mandates that no seller can sell its products exclusively on any marketplace platform, and that all vendors on the e-commerce platform should be provided services in a fair and non-discriminatory manner. Consumers may no longer enjoy the deep discounts offered by retailers that have a close association with marketplace entities. The absence of large retailers will, however, bring relief to small retailers selling on these platforms. Implementation of a new business plan both online sellers and small retailers can earn good level profit, at same time consumer will get good fast will lead business to earn faster and to growth faster in online business world. Some people may think they can build an online empire in their spare time. They put most of their time and effort into their number of job and then fiddle with their business when they feel like it do. Successful online businesses are rarely built this way which If you treat it like a hobby then it will stay a hobby to you. Give

your online business the attention it deserves and treats it like the real business for you.

References:

1. Linden, Greg, Brent Smith, and Jeremy York. "Amazon. com recommendations: Item-to-item collaborative filtering." *IEEE Internet computing* 1 (2003): 76-80.
2. Berinsky, Adam J., Gregory A. Huber, and Gabriel S. Lenz. "Evaluating online labor markets for experimental research: Amazon. com's Mechanical Turk." *Political analysis* 20, no. 3 (2012): 351-368.
3. Laurance, William F., Mark A. Cochrane, Scott Bergen, Philip M. Fearnside, Patricia Delamônica, Christopher Barber, Sammya D'angelo, and Tito Fernandes. "The future of the Brazilian Amazon." *Science* 291, no. 5503 (2001): 438-439.
4. Lewis, Simon L., Paulo M. Brando, Oliver L. Phillips, Geertje MF van der Heijden, and Daniel Nepstad. "The 2010 amazon drought." *Science* 331, no. 6017 (2011): 554-554.
5. Miyazaki, Anthony D., and Ana Fernandez. "Consumer perceptions of privacy and security risks for online shopping." *Journal of Consumer affairs* 35, no. 1 (2001): 27-44.